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THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN AFRICA AND RUSSIA: PROSPECTS AND TASKS FOR THE FUTURE

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Abstract

The article examines the relations between Russia and Africa in historical retrospect. It is shown that many African governments have traditionally maintained and continue to maintain good relations with Moscow, and these ties date back to the Soviet era. Russia has historically been a reliable partner for African countries, as economic and ideological ambitions have often coincided, and ties between Russia and Africa have been strengthened by mutual distrust of Western states.

Keywords: industry, Russia, Africa, Union, trade, agriculture, history.

I. INTRODUCTION

The scramble for Africa is a term widely used by historians to describe the invasion, annexation, division and colonisation of most of Africa by seven western European powers during an era known as "New imperialism" between 1833-1914, the partition of Africa began with the earnest with the Berlin conference of 1884-1885, and was cause of most of Africa's borders today. In this belief period, the prospective colonisers partitioned Africa into spheres of influence, protectorates, colonies and free-trade areas. Roughly 1880 and 1914, the African continent was partitioned into more than 50 colonies. This process is called scramble for Africa. By 1900, a significant part of Africa had been colonized by mainly seven European powers which include: Britain, France, Germany, Belgium, Spain, Portugal and Italy. After the conquest of African decentralized and centralized states, the European powers set about establishing colonial state systems, some of African countries that were led by European powers include: Uganda was led by Britain, Algeria by France, Kenya by Britain, Nigeria by Britain, Mozambique by Portugal, Senegal by France etc. Britain established control over many parts of Africa including Sudan and much of the south, France began to rule a large territory in the west and north Africa.

II. METHODOLOGY AND RESULTS

The methodological bases of the study was dialectical methods of cognition, relying on a wide range of sources and literature on the problem. The research is based on the principles of historicism and objectivity, critical interpretation of the source, systematization and comparative analysis of data, depoliticized approach to

history, scientific impartiality. In general, the methodological bases of the work was the problem-chronological principles, which allows analyzing facts and events in a dialectical way.

In the whole of Africa, we have two countries that were not colonized by European powers, that's Ethiopia and Liberia, the reason why Ethiopia was not colonized is that, it had strong leaders like the Putin of today! And those leaders rejected the colonial rule and Ethiopia by then was a strong country, another reason why it was not colonized is that, the land was very mountainous with poor roads which hindered the transport and communication and it became a problem for colonialists to lead Ethiopia. Another country that was not colonized by European powers is Liberia currently led by George weah, the arsenal fc legend, the reason why it was not colonized is that the land was used as a collecting center of slaves from different parts of Africa and we're later transported through atlantic ocean and took them to work in sugarcane plantations in caribbean region in countries like Jamaica, dominican republic, Trinidad and Tobago etc, others were taken to south America in countries like Brazil, colombia, Ecuador etc that's why you see many Brazilian football players are black like the legend pele, Ronaldinho, venecious junior etc their grand father's we're from Africa and went there as slaves, and a smaller percentage went to North America.

Though colonisation of Africa had got a number of effects both negatives and positives and are shown below, some of negative effects include: Africans lost large tracts of their land to the European settlers, many Africans were forced to live in crowded areas and were never able to regain their land, another effect is that many followers of traditional religion were converted into christianity, they were made to believe that their traditional beliefs were primitive, some traditional political institutions were destroyed and replaced with foreign ones, foreign culture was imposed on Africans without regard for their own culture, this led to the loss of the African culture. The African continent was broken up into political units that later became independent countries. People from the same traditional communities were divided and placed in different countries or colonies. The Africans were forced to trade with the colonial masters much more than with fellow Africans living in neighbouring states. Development within the colonies was not balanced or uniform for example it tended to favour areas occupied by white settlers. Africans were discriminated against and mistreated in their own countries.

They introduced slave trade in Africa, majority of africans were forced to slavery to work in sugarcane plantations in south America, caribbean region like in Jamaica and north America which was against the humanity. Though colonisation of Africa also had got some positive effects and these include: the African people developed a desire to control their own future and worked towards achieving justice and equality, New breeds of animals and crops that could do well under the African climate were introduced. Modern health facilities, formal education and other social services were introduced. Colonialism introduced a common currency which had not existed in the past. It introduced modern machines which are now used in agriculture and industries. it introduced modern methods of communication like the use of phones, radios etc which improved easy communication in Africa.

Many governments in Africa have traditionally maintained good relations with moscow, with ties forged under sovient rule, Russia has historically enjoyed warm relations with African countries as their economic and ideologic ambitions often align and their ties are bolstered by a mutual mistrust of the west. Here in Africa, many western countries they use propaganda telling our people that, there is no democracy in Eastern world countries like in Russia and china, but now africans have opened the eyes and they understand who is right, because they asked themselves in their hearts. Because they spent many years dealing with western countries but they gained nothing and remained poor, now where is democracy there? Democracy means poverty in Africa! Or imposing homosexuality to destroy African culture, so you pray for Uganda because the world bank stopped giving financial aid to my country because that Uganda rejected the homosexuals in the country, the western countries do it intentionally to support civil wars in Africa such that they get minerals like uranium, gold, copper, minerals which are used to make smart phones etc to get them for free or at a low price. Take an example of my neighbors of democratic republic of congo, they have many minerals like uranium, gold, copper, minerals which are used to make smart phones, forests, fertile soils etc but when you look the way how they live, you can cry, they are so poor and their country is among the poorest countries of this world, so because of all these reasons, many African countries have decided to join Russia to save them from western countries and support it to develop by it financially and defense, what we need is development, military equipment is a key factor in the relationship between Africa and Russia.

International Parliamentary Conference "Russia-Africa in a Multipolar World".

Russia is trying to help Africa to develop in nuclear technology by constructing nuclear power plants like in Egypt, Uganda to generate electricity which will lead to the development of Africa. For example, the niger government recently was overthrow Ed by militants and the reason they are giving is their country is rich in uranium and they don't have any nuclear power plant in their country to generate electricity, all the uranium is exported outside and they remain poor, Africa and Russia are planning to cooperate more closely in the higher education and scientific research spheres.

III. CONCLUSION

Russia's strategic engagement in Africa, this project explores Russia's strategic engagement and policy impact on the continent, Russia has commercial, security and political or diplomatic interests in Africa.

One of the main ideological messages that Russia promotes in the African direction is the joint fight against neocolonialism. "Russia and African countries defend the traditional moral norms and social foundations of our peoples and oppose neocolonial ideology imposed from outside," Vladimir Putin said on March 20, 2023, at the International Parliamentary Conference "Russia-Africa in a Multipolar World. - By the way, many states of Asia, the Middle East and Latin America adhere to similar positions, and all together we make up the world majority". Moscow broadcasts this thesis at all levels - for example, one of the key topics at the above-mentioned parliamentary conference was "Western neocolonialism: how to prevent history from repeating itself."

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ВЗАИМООТНОШЕНИЯ МЕЖДУ АФРИКОЙ И РОССИЕЙ: ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ И ЗАДАЧИ НА БУДУЩЕЕ

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Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются отношения между Россией и Африкой в исторической ретроспективе. Показано, что многие правительства африканских стран традиционно поддерживали и продолжают поддерживать хорошие отношения с Москвой, причем эти связи возникли ещё в советское время. Россия исторически была надежным партнером для африканских стран, поскольку экономические и идеологические амбиции часто совпадали, а связи между Россией и Африкой укреплялись взаимным недоверием к западным государствам.

Ключевые слова: промышленность, Россия, Африка, союз, торговля, сельское хозяйство, история.

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